

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D8.4 – Report on reproducibility

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Executive Summary

This deliverable highlights EOSC-Life's contributions to enhancing research reproducibility.

The EOSC-Life project focuses on improving research reproducibility through various strategies including data sharing, standardization of workflows, promotion of FAIR principles, quality control, community engagement, long-term data preservation and training.

The Deliverable assesses the impact of EOSC-Life resources on reproducibility using various Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):

- Usage Statistics: Tracks visits, page views, submissions, and downloads to gauge adoption and practical relevance.
- Citations: Measures resource impact through citations, recognizing that citation patterns vary based on factors like field and utility.

Challenges in interpreting citation data are acknowledged, including varying citation practices, niche audiences, and lag between publication and citation. Not all users cite resources, impacting their recognition. However, the Deliverable highlights evidence of community use of the EOSC-Life resources and related initiatives, that were designed to improve reproducibility.

Data re-use is a pivotal factor in advancing reproducibility within life science research, allowing for independent validation of findings. Re-using data from past or external studies permits the replication of analyses and experiments using the same dataset, affirming the reliability of original results beyond specific analysis methods. The practice enables researchers to contrast their outcomes with prior studies employing similar datasets, unveiling consistent patterns or divergences across analyses, which deepens comprehension of the studied phenomenon.

Pooling data from multiple sources augments statistical power, offering larger sample sizes for more robust conclusions. Data re-use empowers researchers to explore fresh research questions using pre-existing datasets before embarking on new data generation, fostering novel discoveries and insights overlooked by the original authors.

This approach saves time, resources, and costs by capitalizing on pre-collected data, allowing researchers to prioritize analysis and interpretation, thus accelerating scientific progress.

The text highlights a dedicated effort within WP8 (Work Package 8) concerning data re-use assessment and discusses factors impacting this practice. The text presents findings from a literature review on data re-use in ovarian cancer pharmacology and outcomes of a round-table discussion during the final AGM of the project.

Barriers to data re-use are discussed, including awareness, technical complexities, lack of bioinformatics expertise, data quality concerns, publication incentives, and data attribution. The importance of aggregating data in trusted resources for enhanced discoverability, consolidation, standardization, integration, and preservation is emphasized.

Challenges in tracking data re-use and strategies for improvement are outlined, along with recommendations for policies that support data re-use, such as promoting training, fostering collaborations, standardizing metadata, recognizing data usage, and facilitating open sharing of unpublished and negative results data.

In conclusion, the EOSC-Life project significantly contributes to enhancing reproducibility in life science research by fostering open collaboration, standardization, and integration. Its impact is measured through usage statistics and citations, reflecting increased adoption and practical relevance. Collaboration with various data-related initiatives amplifies the project's impact, leading to a connected ecosystem for reproducible and collaborative research in the life sciences.

Moreover, the Deliverable underscores the critical role of data re-use in bolstering reproducibility in life science research. The text emphasizes the benefits of leveraging existing datasets, calls for overcoming barriers to data re-use, and proposes measures to create a supportive environment for fostering data sharing and re-use. These recommendations could be the basis for future projects' activities.

Project Objectives

The EOSC-Life project aimed to enhance the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) by creating an open and collaborative environment for life science research.

As we outlined in the previous deliverable (D8.1), the EOSC-Life project contributes to improving reproducibility in several ways:

- a. **Data Sharing and Open Science:** The project promotes the sharing of life science research data, tools, methodologies, standards, policies, and workflows within the EOSC framework. By making research data openly accessible, it becomes easier for other researchers to replicate experiments and verify findings, enhancing the reproducibility of research results.
- b. **Standardization of Workflows:** EOSC-Life seeks to develop standardized workflows and best practices for various life science research domains. Standardization helps ensure that experiments and analyses of the same type are conducted consistently, making it easier for others to reproduce the results using the same protocols.
- c. **FAIR Principles:** The project follows, implements, and promotes the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles for data management and sharing. These principles aim to make research data more discoverable and reusable by both humans and machines, thereby supporting reproducibility efforts.
- d. **Quality Control and Validation:** EOSC-Life focuses on quality control and validation of data and tools.
- e. **Community Engagement and Collaboration:** The project fosters collaboration among researchers and communities, encouraging active engagement in the development and validation of research tools and workflows. Collaborative efforts often lead to better-validated resources and practices, ultimately improving reproducibility.
- f. **Long-Term Data Preservation:** EOSC-Life aims to provide a sustainable infrastructure for long-term data preservation. Ensuring that data is preserved and remains accessible over time is essential for reproducibility, as it allows others to validate research findings long after the original study was conducted. A wide community effort of the EOSC-Life consortium contributed a recent paper, which clearly describes why science needs to be sustainable and how the sustainability of FAIR science resources and projects can be ensured (David et al., 2023).
- g. **Training and Education:** The project invests in training and education programs to equip researchers with the skills and knowledge necessary to conduct reproducible research. Training on data

management, open science practices, and proper use of openly available and FAIR tools helps researchers adopt reproducibility practices more effectively.

- h. Integration with other data-related initiatives: Integrating with existing initiatives and projects (EOSC and National Initiatives, European Research Infrastructures, ELIXIR Nodes and Services) allows EOSC-Life to leverage existing resources, expertise, and data repositories, fostering collaboration and maximizing the impact of its efforts.

By addressing these aspects, the EOSC-Life project contributed significantly to the improvement of reproducibility in life science research. By creating a collaborative and open ecosystem, the project facilitates the sharing of resources and knowledge, enabling researchers to build upon each other's work and ensure the credibility and transparency of scientific discoveries.

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

1. Measuring impact of EOSC-Life related resources on reproducibility: Usage statistics and citations

In this Deliverable, we refer to the resources developed within EOSC-Life or in related initiatives that we inventoried in the previous deliverable (D8.1). We report Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of such resources, such as number of visits, page views, submissions, and downloads, that provide insights into the adoption and usage of these resources for increasing reproducible research and indicate their practical relevance and impact.

In addition, we provide the number of citations of the paper(s) describing the resource: this can give an independent indication of its use and impact, although we are aware that it may not be a fully reliable measure on its own. In fact, there are several factors to consider when interpreting the number of citations as a measure of a resource's use (each of which could lead to either an over- or an under-estimate of its impact):

- Citations may not appear immediately after the publication of the paper.
- Citation practices can vary across different fields and disciplines: in some areas, researchers may be more likely to cite the paper describing a resource, while in others, they might primarily cite the resource directly.
- Some citations may acknowledge the resource's usefulness and direct contribution to research, while others may only mention it in passing or cite it for historical context.
- Some resources may serve niche research communities or specific purposes, leading to fewer citations, but they could still be highly valuable within their domains.
- Certain types of resources, such as software tools or databases, might be cited less frequently than traditional research papers, even though they are widely used.
- Significant lag between publication and its citation. This is particularly relevant for EOSC-Life related resources as several of them are very recent and it takes time for a recently published resource to be discovered, read, implemented, and cited.

Providing homogeneous information about resource use can be difficult, due to the diverse and unique characteristics of each resource. Each resource serves its own purpose addressing the needs of related research domains, and designed with tailored functionalities - which overall makes standardization of metrics across different resources difficult and in some cases not applicable. The size and profile of the user community can vary significantly between resources. Some resources may have broad appeal and widespread use, while others serve smaller, specialized communities. The impact and importance of a resource can be subjective and context-dependent, making it difficult to assign standardized impact factors. Resources may have different lifespans and rates of evolution. Some resources may be short-term tools for specific projects, while others serve as long-standing, foundational resources.

An additional challenge is that not all users of data and computational resources cite the source. This can be due to several factors, such as unawareness, publication bias, lack of incentives, and may hinder the recognition of impact.

Due to the reasons described above, not all the KPIs were reported for each resource.

However, this Deliverable and the KPIs reported here evidence the use in life science of reproducibility-enhancing strategies across the lifetime of the EOSC-Life project, powered by the resources developed within the project or in related initiatives that we inventoried in the previous deliverable (D8.1).

Tool	Reference period for statistics	Number of submissions	No of visits (sessions)	No of Unique Visitors (users)	No of page views	Reference paper(s) and citations
MICHA https://micha-protocol.org/	Since 1st Jan 2022	–	1584 (monthly average 93)	1058 (monthly average 62)	3944 (monthly average 232)	Tanoli et al., "Minimal information for chemosensitivity assays (MICHA): a next-generation pipeline to enable the FAIRification of drug screening experiments", <i>Brief Bioinform.</i> 2022 Jan 17;23(1): bbab350. doi: 10.1093/bib/bbab350. Cited:6
chEMBL https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chembl/	1st April 2023 to 30th June 2023	Not relevant: most data are extracted by data extractors from the MedChem literature as well as submitted by data depositors and then curated in house	132,586 (monthly average 44,195)	73,659 (monthly average 24,533)	1,745,699 (monthly average 581,899)	Gaulton, Anna, et al. "ChEMBL: a large-scale bioactivity database for drug discovery." <i>Nucleic acids research</i> 40.D1 (2012): D1100-D1107. Cited: 2,194 Bento, A. Patrícia, et al. "The ChEMBL bioactivity database: an update." <i>Nucleic acids research</i> 42.D1 (2014): D1083-D1090. Cited: 978 Gaulton, Anna, et al. "The ChEMBL database in 2017." <i>Nucleic acids research</i> 45.D1 (2017): D945-D954. Cited: 1,175

						Mendez, David, et al. "ChEMBL: towards direct deposition of bioassay data." <i>Nucleic acids research</i> 47.D1 (2019): D930-D940. Cited: 620
ECBD https://ecbd.eu/	since 2021	Datasets submitted to ECBD: 2021, 22; 2022, 11; 2023, 38. ECBD datasets submitted to other repositories: 2023, 5 sets submitted to BY-COVID repository	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
PDB-REDO https://pdb-redo.eu/	1st January 2022 to 31st August 2022	–	147,932 (monthly average 18,492)	97,477 (monthly average 12,185)	720,299 (monthly average 90,037)	pdb-redo papers were cited 328 times in 2022.
Common Workflow Language https://www.commonwl.org/	–	–	–	see https://cwl.discourse.group/c/cwlcon-2021/9 for a list of users	–	over 600 citations and mentions of CWL in published papers and reports (https://www.zotero.org/groups/2294829/cwl/items)
RO-Crate https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/	–	–	–	–	–	Soiland-Reyes, S., Sefton, P., Crosas, M., Castro, L. J., Coppens, F., Fernández, J. M., Garijo, D., Grüning, B., La Rosa, M., Leo, S., Ó Carragáin, E., Portier, M., Trisovic, A., RO-Crate Community, Groth, P., & Goble, C. (2022). Packaging research artefacts with RO-Crate. <i>Data Science</i> , 5(2), 97–138. https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210053 Cited:13

WorkflowHub https://workflows.eurochem.eu/	since 2020	354 workflows, 16 system types, 481 contributions, 165 teams, 9 collections	426K+ total accesses, 5.8k+ downloads	–	–	https://zenodo.org/record/4605654-935_views_536_downloads
COVID-19 WorkflowHub https://workflows.eurochem.eu/tags/57#workflows	since 2020	it is a subset of the workflow, corresponding to 44 workflows	–	–	–	–
FAIRsharing https://fairsharing.org/	Since 2015	3.909 records (https://fairsharing.org/summary-statistics), 1.246 contributors since 2015	–	–	198.000 page visits since 2015 (monthly average 2200)	–
FAIR cookbook https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/home.html	January 2022- January 2023	82 recipes, and 97 authors, as of May 2023	–	13,889 total users	50,418 page views	Rocca-Serra, P., Gu, W., Ioannidis, V. et al. The FAIR Cookbook - the essential resource for and by FAIR doers. <i>Sci Data</i> 10, 292 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02166-3
Provenance standard under ISO 276 (ISO 23494)	See text	–	–	–	–	The first part of ISO 23494 is available at: https://www.iso.org/standard/80715.html
Research Data Management kit (RMD Kit) https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/	1st Jan 2022 to 31st August 2022	–	15,627 (monthly average 1954)	5,849 (monthly average 732)	37,067 (monthly average of 4634)	–

Table 1 reports a summary of impact data for the resources inventoried and described in the previous deliverable (D8.1).

MICHA

MICHA (Minimal Information for Chemosensitivity Assays) is a pipeline to enable the FAIRification of drug screening experiments, developed by EATRIS within EOSC-Life (Tanoli et al., 2022). Chemosensitivity assays are commonly used for preclinical drug discovery and clinical trial optimization. However, data from independent assays are often discordant, largely attributed to uncharacterized variation in the experimental materials and protocols. Existing efforts often lack support from data integration tools.

MICHA, on the other hand, can automatically extract publicly available information to facilitate the assay annotation including compounds, samples, reagents, and data processing methods. It provides an integrative web server and database to obtain compound annotation including chemical structures, targets, and disease indications. In addition, MICHA eases the annotation of cell line/patient samples, assay protocols and literature references by retrieving manually curated catalogues and exports a report that conforms to the FAIR principle of drug screening studies.

FAIRified protocols from 5 major cancer drug screening studies as well as 6 recently conducted COVID-19 studies consolidate the utility of MICHA. This dataset is available online¹.

ChEMBL

ChEMBL (Chemical Biology Database) is a widely recognized and extensively used resource in the field of drug discovery and chemical biology. It is a database managed by the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) that provides information on bioactive small molecules and their biological activities, including binding affinities to proteins and other target molecules. The impact of ChEMBL can be seen in various aspects of drug discovery and research:

- **Drug Discovery and Development:** ChEMBL serves as a valuable resource for drug discovery researchers, allowing them to access comprehensive data on the bioactivity of small molecules. This data helps researchers identify potential drug candidates, evaluate their binding to specific targets, and prioritize compounds for further development.
- **Target Identification and Validation:** ChEMBL contains information on the interactions of small molecules with various target proteins. This data is crucial for target identification and validation, helping researchers understand the molecular mechanisms involved in disease and identifying potential therapeutic targets.

ChEMBL data is widely used in computational drug design and virtual screening approaches. Computational methods can leverage the bioactivity information to predict potential ligands for specific targets, aiding in the design of new drugs and optimization of existing ones.

ChEMBL's extensive data on bioactivities allows researchers to conduct pharmacological profiling of small molecules. This information helps characterize the selectivity and off-target effects of compounds, contributing to the development of safer and more effective drugs.

ChEMBL adheres to the principles of open science by providing open access to its data. This promotes transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration in drug discovery research.

ECBD

The ECBD (European Chemical Biology Database) of EU-OPENSREEN is a resource that plays a significant role in chemical biology research and drug discovery efforts. ECBD serves as a central repository for storing and sharing chemical biology data generated through these screening efforts.

ECBD

¹ <https://micha-protocol.org/protocols/index>.

- houses a vast collection of chemical screening data, including information on bioactive compounds and their biological activities. By providing access to this data, ECBD enables researchers to identify potential drug candidates more efficiently, accelerating the drug discovery process.
- serves as a collaborative platform, allowing researchers to share their screening data and findings with the broader scientific community. This fosters knowledge exchange, encourages collaboration, and prevents duplication of efforts in chemical biology research.
- enforces data standardization and quality control, ensuring that the shared data is reliable and consistent. Standardized data enhances data comparability and enables more robust analyses.
- adheres to principles of open science by providing open access to chemical biology data. Open access promotes transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration in the scientific community.

The official announcement of ECBD was made in June 2023 and so far, the authors are in the process of the integration of a web-page analytics software. Therefore, no user statistics are available at the moment.

PDB-REDO

PDB-REDO (Protein Data Bank - REfinement of Data) is a computational method and resource used for improving the quality of protein structures deposited in the Protein Data Bank (PDB). Its impact lies in the significant improvements it makes to the accuracy and reliability of protein structures, thereby enhancing the quality of structural biology research.

Some of the PDB papers describe multiple resources so the citation metrics can be a bit of an overestimation. The resource had a huge peak in usage at the first corona year due to the lockdowns. The usage is now normal again with a gradual rise.

Common workflow language

The Common Workflow Language (CWL) is a standardized specification for describing data analysis workflows and tools in a way that is portable and easily reproducible across different computing environments [Citation]. CWL has had a significant impact on the field of bioinformatics and computational biology, as well as other data-intensive scientific domains. Its focus on reproducibility, interoperability, and resource efficiency has made it a valuable tool for researchers seeking to streamline their data analysis workflows and foster open, collaborative, and efficient research practices. The CWL standards have become central to a diverse community of users across multiple fields of science and engineering.

RO-crate

Research Object Crate (RO-Crate) is a community-driven specification and toolset for packaging, describing, and sharing research data and related resources. It is designed to enhance the FAIRness of research data by providing a standardized format for creating self-contained data packages (Soiland-Reyes et al., 2022).

Workflowhub

WorkflowHub is an open-access platform designed to host and share scientific workflows from various domains, including bioinformatics, data science, computational biology, and other research fields.

WorkflowHub has the potential to make a significant impact on the scientific community by fostering reproducibility, collaboration, and standardization in computational research. By providing an open and accessible platform for sharing workflows, it facilitates knowledge exchange and encourages researchers to embrace open science practices, ultimately advancing scientific discovery and innovation.

FAIR Sharing and FAIR Cookbook

We report the information for FAIRsharing, as FAIR assist (mentioned in D8.1) is part of it.

FAIRsharing has a wide impact at the European Commission level. In fact, it is recommended by the Horizon Europe Programme Guide² and many other EOSC reports³.

In addition, it is recommended by major publishers⁴; by the RDA and other global organizations⁵, and its content powers a growing number of tools and services⁶.

FAIR Cookbook is among the ELIXIR flagship resources⁷, and it is embedded in the ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2024-2028. At European Commission level, it is recommended by the IMI/IHI Project Guidelines for “Open Access to Publication and Research Data”⁸ and by the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023-2024 for Health⁹.

Provenance standard under ISO 276 (ISO 23494)

The potential impact of a provenance standard, which refers to the documentation and tracking of the origins and history of data, processes, and resources, is wide. Provenance standards aim to provide transparency and accountability, especially in scientific research and data-intensive domains.

The first part of ISO 23494 is available at the ISO webpage¹⁰.

This result already demonstrates that the initiative is having a global impact, since this meant reaching global consensus. In fact, ISO is comprised of national mirror committees which are then represented in ISO itself and comment/vote on standards. Hence this alignment was necessary before approving the standard.

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

³ <https://fairsharing.org/communities#adopters>

⁴ <https://fairsharing.org/communities#publishers>

⁵ <https://fairsharing.org/communities#organisations>

⁶ <https://fairsharing.org/communities#tools>

⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/what-we-offer/guidelines>

⁸ https://www.imi.europa.eu/sites/default/files/uploads/documents/resources-for-projects/IMI2_OpenAcesGuidelines_Updated2021.pdf

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2023-2024/wp-4-health_horizon-2023-2024_en.pdf

¹⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/80715.html>

The other activities on the standardization process have been going on until the end of the project, as planned, and it is impossible to expect their adoption before this period.

2. Data reuse

Data re-use plays a critical role in contributing to reproducibility in life science research. When researchers re-use data generated by themselves or others, it allows independent verification and validation of research findings, which are fundamental aspects of reproducibility.

By re-using data from a previous study, researchers can attempt to reproduce the original analysis or experiment using the same dataset. This independent verification helps validate the robustness and reliability of the original findings, ensuring that the results are not dependent on a specific analysis pipeline or data processing method.

Data re-use enables researchers to compare their findings with those of previous studies that used the same or similar datasets. Such comparative studies can help identify consistent patterns or discrepancies across different analyses, leading to a deeper understanding of the phenomenon under investigation.

In some cases, combining data from multiple studies can lead to more statistically powerful analyses. Re-using data from different sources allows for larger sample sizes, increasing the generalizability of the results and enhancing the robustness of the conclusions.

Data re-use allows researchers to explore new research questions and hypotheses using existing datasets before generating new data. This can lead to novel discoveries with already available information and insights that were not initially considered by the original authors.

Re-using data can save time, resources, and costs since the data collection phase is already completed. Researchers can focus on the analysis and interpretation, accelerating the pace of scientific research.

A particular effort has been dedicated within WP8 to the assessment of actual data re-use within the life science community and discussion of the factors that may limit this practice.

We report here the results of a literature review assessing data re-use in the field of ovarian cancer pharmacology and the conclusions of a round-table discussion held during the final AGM of the project.

Review of data re-use on ovarian cancer pharmacology

We want to address here a particular aspect of reproducibility which is external validity, that is, obtaining an equivalent outcome from an independent experiment or observation conducted in different conditions (experimental model, animal species, outcome measurements, ...) from the original experiment.

In particular, the concept of low external validity of preclinical research, for instance in the context of *in vivo* disease experimental models, refers to the limited generalizability or applicability of research findings from these models to real-world clinical situations or human populations. While *in vivo* disease models are essential tools for studying diseases, testing interventions, and understanding underlying mechanisms, they may have limitations that affect their ability to accurately represent the complexities of human traits.

Therefore, the transition from preclinical studies in animals to effective treatments in humans (clinical translation) is complex and often faces challenges. For these reasons, it is essential to complement findings from animal models with evidence from other, particularly human, studies. We wanted to test the hypothesis that the contextual use of data from public datasets may improve the external validity of animal studies.

With this objective, we decided to perform a systematic review of the literature, restricting to the field of ovarian cancer.

As a first step, a systematic search of Medline and EMBASE databases was carried out to identify epithelial ovarian cancer clinical trials assessing the antitumor activity of candidate compounds (CC) as monotherapy. Then, for each eligible CC, a systematic search was carried out to identify scientific papers reporting *in vivo* experiments on rats and mice, in which the CC was administered as monotherapy.

An initial review was performed by Luca Porcu¹¹ for the period 2010-2019. We then updated the search to October 2022.

A common methodological approach has been applied to systematically retrieve, appraise, and summarize data from the various clinical trials. Studies were identified through systematic searches of two major literature databases: MedLine and EMBASE.

The selection of the studies to be included in the analysis was made by two independent reviewers who screened the titles and abstracts of the retrieved records to exclude any clearly irrelevant records. Secondly, we retrieved and checked the full publications of possibly eligible records to confirm or not their inclusion in the analysis. All the discrepancies were resolved by discussion between the two reviewers.

Figure 1: Number of studies reporting data re-use, before or after 2006, among the surveyed preclinical studies (2010-2019) (A). Main characteristics of the 5 selected studies

The results of the first review, summarized in Figure 1, showed a very low occurrence of data re-use in this particular field. The update found 7 new papers, only 1 of them reporting re-use.

With these low numbers, it was impossible to test our primary hypothesis, which was to demonstrate that data re-use can impact external reproducibility. Instead, this led us to open a discussion within EOSC-Life on possible reasons for this.

Preclinical researchers may make limited use of data in public datasets for several reasons.

¹¹ <https://oro.open.ac.uk/72299/>

They may not be aware of the availability of relevant public datasets or may not be familiar with the processes for accessing and using these resources. In addition, integrating data from different sources and platforms can be technically complex and time-consuming. Preclinical researchers may not have the necessary bioinformatics or computational expertise to effectively merge and analyse diverse datasets. The elevated average number of authors with computational skills in the “re-using” papers demonstrates that this would not be possible for researchers with a pure biomedical background.

Another relevant obstacle could be related to trust. Researchers might be concerned about the quality, accuracy, and reliability of data in public datasets. Without assurance of data validity, preclinical researchers may be hesitant to integrate external data into their work.

In some cases, researchers may prioritize generating novel data for publication, as original research is often more valued in terms of career advancement and recognition, as well as in term of funding. The same could be true for journal policies.

3. Next steps

To follow up on this subject, and to respond to a more general interest, WP8 organized a round table on data re-use during the final EOSC-Life AGM, June 2023.

Several key points were addressed in the discussion.

Data re-use underestimation

Apart from the results of the review in the field of preclinical ovarian cancer research, several considerations point to the possibility that data re-use could be largely underestimated.

First of all, there may be a significant time lag between data reuse and the availability of metrics or tracking data, especially if researchers do not immediately publish their work and make the data openly available through data repositories.

Another challenge is represented by a possibly limited data and resources use attribution. Initiatives promoting data citation practices, persistent identifiers (such as DOIs) for datasets, and standardized metadata contribute to improved data attribution and tracking. Additionally, the adoption of FAIR data principles and data management plans that include data reuse tracking strategies can help in capturing more comprehensive metrics of data reuse in the future.

In particular, the use of big reference databases, such as those containing genomic data, protein structures, medical records, or environmental data, often serve as valuable resources for researchers working in various fields, but it is so common practice that it is not considered as a data re-use.

Big reference databases are typically curated, maintained, and made available to the scientific community for reuse. They provide valuable datasets that have been collected and organized with high-quality standards, making them reliable sources for researchers to draw upon for their own investigations. This data reuse contributes to a more efficient and sustainable research ecosystem, as it promotes the sharing of knowledge and data resources.

Human genetic data orientated resources have had a profound and transformative impact on biomedical research, healthcare, and our understanding of human genetics. These resources, made available

through various databases and initiatives, have accelerated scientific discoveries, enabled personalized medicine, and advanced our knowledge of the genetic basis of health and disease.

Unlike citation metrics for publications, there are no standardized metrics or identifiers to track data reuse effectively, and there is no standardized approach for measuring the extent of data reuse consistently across different platforms. Datasets in resources are very often given accession numbers that can be cited in publications. However, the reporting of the accession numbers of datasets used in publication(s) is not standardised, and this could be a reason for under reporting. Moreover, not all data that is reused comes from datasets that are recorded in repositories, etc. and therefore do not have accession numbers in the first place. An additional problem is represented by the case of negative results data, or data that does not make it to be included into a publication. In addition, sometimes data may be re-used for explorative purposes or for some controls and the questions is to what extent this re-use is systematically cited.

Data reuse may occur over extended periods, in different ways, and databases may not continuously track and report every instance of reuse. Long-term reuse may be underrepresented in usage statistics.

Finally, users could be a) searching for a particular data set, b) viewing a particular data set, c) exploring / analysing a data set on the platform where the data is hosted, d) downloading a data set and e) referring to a data set re-used in studies. At what step can the data be considered as re-used is to be defined.

Reuse is facilitated if data are aggregated in larger and more trusted resources

Aggregating data in larger and more trusted resources can significantly facilitate data reuse and have several benefits for researchers and the scientific community as a whole. Here are some ways in which data aggregation in trusted resources promotes data reuse:

- **Increased Discoverability:** Larger and trusted data resources (such, for instance PDB, IDR, BIA, EMPIAR, ECBD) often have better search and discovery capabilities. Researchers can easily find relevant datasets within these resources, making it more likely that they will come across data suitable for their research needs.
- **Consolidation of Data:** Data aggregation brings together datasets from various sources, allowing researchers to access a diverse and comprehensive collection of data. This consolidation may be challenging, but it saves time and effort by avoiding the need to search for and access individual datasets from multiple locations. FAIRsharing provides a very nice example of a consolidation strategy.
- **Data Standardization:** Trusted data resources typically adhere to data standards and best practices. This standardization enhances data quality and ensures that the data is well-documented and reliable, making it easier for researchers to understand and reuse the data.
- **Data Integration and Interoperability:** Aggregating data in larger resources promotes data integration and interoperability. Researchers can combine data from different sources more effectively, enabling cross-study analyses and meta-analyses.
- **Long-Term Data Preservation:** Trusted data resources often prioritize data preservation, ensuring that valuable data remains accessible and usable over time. Long-term data availability promotes data reuse even years after the original data collection.

- **Data Attribution and Citation:** Larger and trusted resources often have established data citation practices. This encourages researchers to properly attribute the data they use, ensuring credit is given to the data creators.
- **Facilitating Data Sharing:** Data aggregation in trusted resources encourages researchers to contribute their data to a shared repository. This strengthens the culture of data sharing and encourages more researchers to make their data available for reuse.

Policies deemed to favour data re-use

- Promote **training** and access to **consultation** by FAIR data experts.
- Foster **collaborations** and interactions between life science researchers and data scientists to promote awareness and understanding of available datasets and tools.
- Enhance and standardise the **metadata and contextual information** associated with public datasets to help researchers assess their relevance and applicability.
- **Recognize and incentivize** the use of public datasets through academic and professional recognition.
- Establish and facilitate solutions and policies for open sharing of good quality unpublished data and **negative results** data.

By creating a more supportive environment for data sharing and reuse, the combined effort of data scientists and biomedical researchers can harness the potential of public datasets to enhance their research and contribute to scientific advancements.

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Delivery and Schedule

The delivery is delayed: No

Adjustments

Adjustments made: None

Appendices

Inclusion criteria for clinical studies:

1. Histologically or cytologically confirmed diagnosis of epithelial ovarian cancer, fallopian tube cancer, or primary peritoneal cancer
2. Assessment of CCs' antitumor activity was the primary or co-primary objective. At least one antitumor activity endpoint was a primary or co-primary endpoint
3. Women aged 18 years or older
4. ECOG/WHO performance status (PS) 0-2 or GOG PS 0-2 (Oken et al., 1982; Rubin et al., 2004)
5. Patients must have failed at least one prior line of platinum-based chemotherapy
6. Study protocol approved by the independent ethics committees or institutional review boards of the participating institutions
7. The final study report was published on 1st January 2010 or later
8. The final study report was written in English

Note: if inclusion criteria of the EOC clinical trials were broader but all patients evaluated for antitumor activity satisfied all previous α 1 criteria, the clinical trial was considered eligible. For instance, if eligible criteria admitted the enrolment of children and all effectively enrolled patients were adults, EOC clinical trial was considered eligible.

Inclusion criteria for candidate compound (CC) in vivo experimental studies

1. CC was evaluated in monotherapy as experimental treatment (i.e. active arm)
2. Monoclonal antibodies, oncolytic viruses or reoviruses, vaccines, immunotherapeutic and endocrine CCs were excluded
3. CC was administered in maintenance therapy
4. CC was administered as standard treatment (i.e., control arm)

PRISMA flow diagram on selection of clinical trials (2010-2019)

PRISMA flow diagram on selection of clinical trials (2019-2022)

PRISMA flow diagram on selection of *in vivo* experimental studies (for CC in 2010-2019 clinical trials)

PRISMA flow diagram on selection of in vivo experimental studies (for CC in 2019-2022 clinical trials)

PRISMA flow diagram on selection of new in vivo experimental studies (2010-2022)